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Review Article

Mouth Dissolving Tablets: A Comprehensive Review on Technologies, Research, Patents, and Marketed Products.

Kalyani Kondapalli*, Yelumarthi Renuka, M. Yamini, Nalli Likhitha, Sanapala Usharani

Raghu College of Pharmacy, Visakhapatnam.

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ABSTRACT

The oral route of administration is currently the gold standard in pharmaceuticals, valued for its safety, patient compliance, and economic advantages, which contribute to its high patient compliance. MDTs' format enables them to disintegrate or dissolve rapidly in the mouth, through the incorporation of super disintegrants, such as croscarmellose sodium, sodium starch glycolate, and crospovidone, which act through mechanisms including swelling, wicking (capillary action), and deformation recovery, eliminating the need for water and making it easier to take medications. Such tablets disintegrate or dissolve in saliva in less than 60 seconds. The formulation's popularity and utility led to the creation of multiple MDT technologies. MDTs are a valuable alternative for patients with dysphagia, offering improved reliability and ease of use for children, the elderly, and mentally ill patients. The Pharmaceutical market has seen a rise in fast-dissolving products, with many new launches in the past 2 to 3 years. This growth is also reflected in the increasing use of fast-dissolving technology for new drug development. This article provides an overview of key attributes, benefits, limitations, formulation considerations, technological approaches, assessment methods, and prospects.

INTRODUCTION

The oral route is the most effective route, despite all the other advanced drug delivery systems. This is due to enhanced patient compliance and convenience for the administrator. Tablets are a frequently prescribed oral dose type that have

properties like their firmness, convenience of production, and accessibility. Along with these advantages, tablets have some major disadvantages, such as difficulty in swallowing for geriatric and pediatric patients and conditions like dysphagia. Hence, mouth-dissolving tablets were developed.

***Corresponding Author:** Kalyani Kondapalli

Address: Raghu College of Pharmacy, Visakhapatnam.

Email ✉: kalyanikondapalli80@gmail.com

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Mouth dissolving tablets are defined as “The solid dosage forms that rapidly disintegrate and dissolve into saliva in the oral cavity, resulting in solution without the need for water for administration”. The technology involved in mouth-dissolving tablets makes the tablets disintegrate in the mouth without chewing, and additional water intake has drawn a greater deal of attention. Mouth dissolving tablets are also known as: fast melting tablets, rapid dissolve tablets, rapid melt tablets, fast dispersing tablets, freeze-dried wafers, and quick disintegrating tablets. These were approved by the Food and Drug Administration and classified as orally disintegrating tablets. The term Oro-dispersible tablet for MDT was recognized by the European pharmacopoeia, which means that, tablet dissolves and disintegrates in less than 3 minutes in the mouth before swallowing. A tablet disintegrates into smaller granules and melts in the mouth, resulting in a hard, solid, to gel-like structure. This allows easy swallowing by the patients. The disintegration time for the mouth-dissolving tablets varies from about seconds to minutes. Mouth dissolving tablets have gained popularity due to their Self-administration capabilities, absence of need for water, and rapid disintegration and dissolution.

ADVANTAGES^{1,2}

- Improve stability
- Ease of administration to patients who are unable to swallow. Ideal for the elderly, pediatrics, geriatric, and psychiatric patients, and people with renal illness.
- Enhance mouth feel and taste masking: The mouth-feel properties of fast-dissolving tablets contribute to the positive shift in the perception of drugs. This is particularly in children, where FDTs can improve the taste of bitter medication.

- Does not require water for administration, especially while travelling.
- No risk of suffocation and choking during mouth dissolving tablets uptake, and helpful in some cases, like motion sickness during coughing, etc.
- Cost-effective
- No chewing needed
- Good chemical stability as a conventional oral solid dosage form
- Benefits of liquid medication in the form of solid medication
- No specific packaging is required. Can be packed in push-through blisters.
- It has a good mouth feel property that helps to take the medication easily, the bitter pill in pediatric patients

DISADVANTAGES^{1,2}:

- Oral dissolving tablets are hygroscopic in nature, so they must be kept in a dry place.
- ODT requires special packaging for proper stabilization and safety of the stable product.
- Brittleness: FDTs can be extremely brittle, especially when molded and compressed at low force. This brittleness, advanced peel-off blister packaging, and posing challenges in production.
- The tablets often do not have enough mechanical strength, and careful handling is required as a result.
- If the pills are not prepared properly, they may have a poor taste and feel gritty in the mouth.

FORMULATION ACCEPTS OF MDTs^{3,4}:

Ingredients used in the formulation of MDTs must allow quick release of the drug, resulting in faster dissolution. This includes both active pharmaceutical ingredient (drug) and excipient (additives).

A. Selection of Drug Candidate: While selecting an appropriate drug candidate for developing an MDT, several candidates must be considered. The ultimate characteristics of a drug for dissolution in the mouth include:

1. Free from bitter taste
2. Dose lower than 20 mg
3. Good solubility in water and saliva
4. Partially unionized at the oral cavity Ph
5. Small to moderate molecular weight
6. Ability to permeate at oral mucosal tissue
7. Ability to diffuse and partition in the epithelium of upper GIT ($\log > 1$ or preferably > 2)

There are no particular limitations for the active pharmaceutical ingredient. Researchers have formulated mouth dissolving films with different drug categories such as analgesics, anti-allergics, anxiolytics, anti-bacterial agents, cardiovascular agents, neuroleptics, etc.

The characteristics that may render unsuitable of drug delivery as MDTs are:

1. Short half-life
2. Unacceptable taste
3. Require controlled or sustained release
4. Combination with anticholinergics

B. Selection of excipients: Excipients used in MDTs should contain at least one disintegrant, a lubricant, a diluent, a sweetener, a flavoring agent, etc. The excipients used are:

1. Superdisintegrants: Superdisintegrants are added to the tablets to aid in the breakup of compacted mass when it is kept in a fluid environment. Super disintegration increases the rate of disintegration and hence dissolution. Superdisintegrant addition is a

common method for preparing MDTs because of its simplicity and affordability. Although superdisintegrants primarily affect the rate of disintegration, using them at high levels can also affect tablet hardness, friability, and mouth feel, so the right amount of Superdisintegrant is to be added to achieve MDTs. Selecting the right Superdisintegrant is very important. There are different factors to be considered while selecting a Superdisintegrant.

- The pill should dissolve in the mouth as soon as it comes into contact with saliva
- It should provide the patient with a satisfying mouth feel
- Small particle size should be used for patient compliance
- It should be compressed to create less fragile tablets
- It should have good flow, since it improves the flow characteristics of the total blend.

Superdisintegrants involve four different mechanisms by which a tablet is broken down into smaller particles. The mechanisms involved are:

- **Swelling:** Swelling is the most accepted mechanism of action for tablet disintegration. Tablets that have high porosity show poor disintegration due to a lack of sufficient swelling force. On the other hand, tablets with low porosity show sufficient swelling force and hence good disintegration.
- **Porosity and capillary action:** Disintegration by capillary action is always the first step. When we put a tablet into a suitable aqueous medium, the medium penetrates the tablet and replaces the air adsorbed on the particles, which weakens the intermolecular bond and breaks the tablet into fine particles. Water uptake by tablets

depends upon the hydrophilicity of the drug/excipient and on tableting conditions. For these types of disintegrants, maintenance of porous structure and low interfacial tension towards aqueous fluid is necessary, which helps in disintegration by creating a hydrophilic network around the drug particles.

- **Due to disintegrating particle/particle repulsive forces:** Another mechanism of disintegrants attempts to explain the swelling of a tablet made with 'non-swelling' disintegrants. Guyot-Hermann has proposed a particle repulsion theory based on the observation that non-swelling particles also cause the disintegration of tablets. The electric repulsive forces between particles are the mechanism of disintegration, and water is required for this process. Researchers found that repulsive is secondary to wicking.
- **Due to deformation:** Disintegrated gets deformed during tablet compression. These deformed particles get into the normal structure when they come in contact with aqueous media or water. Occasionally, the swelling capacity of starch was improved when granules were extensively deformed during compression. The increase in size of deformed particles produces a breakup of the tablet. This may be a mechanism of starch and has recently begun to be studied.

Examples of superdisintegrants include carboxymethyl cellulose, sodium carboxymethyl cellulose, sodium starch glycolate, croscopovidone, microcrystalline cellulose, and modified corn starch.

2. **Binder:** It helps to maintain the integrity of the dosage form before administration. The examples of binders are PVP, PVA, HPMC, etc.

3. **Lubricants:** Lubricant helps to reduce friction. The examples of lubricants are stearic acid, magnesium stearate, magnesium lauryl sulfate, talc, polyethylene glycol, liquid paraffin, colloidal silicon dioxide, etc.
4. **Fillers:** Fillers enhance the bulk of the dosage form. The examples of fillers are calcium carbonate, magnesium carbonate, calcium sulfate, calcium phosphate, aluminum hydroxide, magnesium trisilicate, xylitol, etc.
5. **Emulsifying agents:** Emulsifying agents are useful in stabilizing the immiscible blends and enhancing bioavailability. The examples of emulsifying agents are propylene glycol esters, lecithin, alkyl sulfates, sucrose esters, etc.
6. **Coloring agents:** Coloring agents enhance the appearance and organoleptic properties of the dosage form. The examples of coloring agents are sunset yellow, red iron oxide, Amaranth, etc.
7. **Flavoring agents:** Flavoring agents are used to mask unpleasant taste. Flavoring agents include artificial sweeteners like aspartame, dextrose, maltose, mannitol, sorbitol, vanilla, oils, fruit essence, etc.

PRE FORMULATION STUDIES^{5,6}:

1. **Bulk Density:** Bulk density is measured by pouring the powder (passed through a standard sieve number # 20) into a measuring cylinder, and the initial weight is noted, which is called bulk volume. From this bulk density is calculated from the formula mentioned below.

$$D_b = \frac{M}{V_b}$$

Where M is the mass of powder

V_b is the bulk volume of the powder.

It is expressed in g/ml.

2. **Tapped Density:** Tapped density is the ratio of the total mass of the powder to the tapped volume of the powder. The total mass of the powder was measured, and the tapped volume of the powder was measured by tapping the powder 750 times. Tapping was continued until the difference between successive volumes was less than 2%. If it is more than 2% tapping is continued for 1250 times, and the tapped volume is noted. It is expressed in g/ml.

$$D_t = \frac{M}{V_t}$$

Where M is the mass of powder

V_t is the tapped volume of the powder.

3. **Angle of Repose:** The angle of repose is measured by the friction forces in a loose powder. It is defined as the maximum angle possible between the surface of the pile of powder and the horizontal plane.

The powder was allowed to flow through the funnel. The angle of repose was calculated by measuring the height and radius of the pile of powder.

$$\tan(\theta) = \frac{h}{r}$$

$$\theta = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{h}{r}\right)$$

Where θ is the angle of repose.

h is the height in cms

r is the radius in cms.

Table 1: Relationship between angle of repose and powder flow

Sr No	Angle of Repose	Type of Flow
1.	<20	Excellent
2.	20 - 30	Good
3.	30-40	Passable
4.	>34	Very poor

4. **Carr's index (or) % Compressibility:** It indicates powder flow properties. It is expressed in percentage and is given by

$$I = \frac{D_t - D_b}{D_t} \times 100$$

Where, D_t is the tapped density of the powder

D_b is the bulk density of the powder

Table 2: Relationship between % compressibility and flow ability

% Compressibility	Flow ability
5 – 12	Excellent
12 – 16	Good
18 – 21	Fair Passable
23 – 35	Poor
33 – 3	Very poor
< 40	Very very poor

5. **Hausner ratio:** The Hausner ratio is an indirect index of ease of powder flow. It is calculated by the following formula.

$$\text{Hausner ratio} = \frac{D_t}{D_b}$$

Where, D_t is the tapped density.

D_b is the bulk density.

A lower Hausner ratio (<1.25) indicates better flow properties than a higher one (>1.25).

6. **Void volume:** The volume of the spaces is known as the void volume. It is given by a formula

$$V = V_b - V_p$$

Where, V_b = Bulk volume (volume before tapping)
 V_p = The volume (volume after tapping)

7. **Porosity:** The porosity of the powder is the ratio of void volume to the bulk volume of the packing. The porosity of powder indicates the types of packaging a powder undergoes when it is subjected to vibrations, when stored, or in a tablet machine when passed through a hopper. Porosity is calculated by using the formula:

$$\text{Porosity} = \frac{V_b - V_p}{V_p} = \frac{1 - V_p}{V_b}$$

Porosity is frequently expressed in percentage. It is given by:

$$\% \text{ porosity} = \left(\frac{1 - V_p}{V_b} \right) \times 100$$

8. **Identification of drug sample:** It was confirmed by melting point determination and also by FT-IR spectral analysis
9. **Drug excipient Compatibility study:** The compatibility of the drug with excipients was determined by FT-IR spectral analysis. This study was carried out to detect any changes in the chemical constitution of the drug after it was combined with the excipients. The samples were taken for the FT-IR study

EVALUATION TESTS FOR MOUTH DISSOLVING TABLETS^{7,8}:

1. **Weight variation:** The weight variation test is conducted to ensure uniformity in the weight of tablets within a batch. The total weight of 20 tablets from each formulation is determined and calculated. The individual weight of each tablet is determined to find out the weight variation.

Table 3: Uniformity of weight according to USP Specification

Sr. No	Average weight of tablets (mg)	Maximum % difference allowed
1.	130 or less	10
2.	130 – 324	7.5
3.	More than 324	5

2. **Hardness:** Hardness or tablet crushing strength (f_c), the force required to break a tablet in a diametric compression, was measured using the Monsanto tablet hardness tester. It is expressed in kg/cm^2 .
3. **Friability test:** Friability test is done to assess the ability of the tablet to withstand abrasion in packing, handling, and transport. Friability is the loss of weight of tablets due to the removal of fine particles from the surface. The Roche friabilator is used for finding the friability of the tablets. Weigh 20 tablets from each batch and then place them in the Roche friabilator. Rotate the Roche friabilator at 25 rpm for 4 minutes. Dedust the tablets and weigh again. The percentage of friability is calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{ Friability} = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_1} \times 100$$

Where, W_1 = weight of tablet before test
 W_2 = weight of tablet after test

4. **Disintegration test:**

In – vivo disintegration test: *In – vivo* disintegration test is carried out on 2 or 3 tablets in the mouth, and the time taken to disintegrate the complete tablet is noted.

In – vitro disintegration test: *In – vitro* disintegration test is measured by dropping a tablet in the beaker containing 50 ml of Sorenson's buffer pH 6.8. Three tablets from each formulation

are randomly selected, and *in vitro* dispersion is carried out.

5. **In – Vitro Dissolution test:** *In – Vitro* Dissolution test is carried out using USP Type II Apparatus, i.e., paddle type at 50 rpm. 900ml phosphate buffer pH 6.8 is used as dissolution medium, maintained at 37 ± 0.5 . Withdraw the sample of 10 ml at specific time intervals of 2 minutes and filter. The amount of drug dissolved is determined by a suitable analytical technique.
6. **Wetting time:** The wetting time of tablets is measured by placing the five circular tissue papers of 10 cm diameter in a petri dish containing 0.2%w/v solution (3ml). A tablet is carefully placed on tissue paper. The time required for developing blue color on the surface of the tablet is noted as wetting time.
7. **Water absorption ratio:** A small piece of tissue paper folded twice is placed in a small Petri dish containing 6 ml of water. Put a tablet on the paper. The time required for complete wetting is measured. The wetted tablet is then weighed. Water absorption ratio is measured by using a formula

$$R = 100 \times \frac{W_a - W_b}{W_b}$$

Where,

W_b is the weight of the tablet before water absorption

W_a is the weight of the tablet after water absorption

8. **Uniformity of dispersion:** Two tablets are placed in 100 ml of water and stirred gently for 2 minutes. The dispersion is passed through mesh 22. The tablets, uniformity will

be considered passing if no residue remains on the screen.

9. **Stability Studies:** The optimized formulation of MDTs is subjected to a stability study as per ICH guidelines to assess their stability with respect to physical appearance.

TECHNOLOGIES USED FOR THE FORMULATION OF MOUTH-DISSOLVING TABLETS⁹:

There are several technologies used in the formulation of mouth dissolving tablets, namely (1) Conventional technologies. (2) Patented technologies.

Table 4: Different Conventional and Patented technologies

Conventional Technologies	Patented Technologies
Freeze Drying	Zydis technologies
Tablet Molding	Orasolv technologies
Direct Compression	Durasolv technologies
Sublimation	Wowtab technologies

Conventional technologies for mouth-dissolving tablets:

There are many conventional technologies for the formulation of MDTs. They are:

- (1) **Freeze-drying method:** Freeze-drying technology is one of the best methods for the formulation of mouth-dissolving tablets. It is also called Lyophilization. In this method, an amorphous porous structure is created that can be rapidly dissolved. Lyophilization is a process in which water is sublimed from the product after freezing. This results in preparations, which are highly porous, with a very high specific surface area, that dissolve rapidly and improve absorption and bioavailability.

(2) **Tablet Molding:** These are of two types of molding processes. The solvent method and the heat method. The solution method involves moistening the powder blend with a hydro- alcoholic solvent, followed by compression at low pressures in molded plates to form a wetted mass (compression molding). Below, Air-drying is done to remove the solvent. The tablets manufactured in so form are low compact. Whereas in the heat molding process, a suspension is prepared that contains the drug, agar, and sugars like mannitol and lactose. This suspension is poured into the blister packaging wells, resulting in the formation of jelly, and is dried at 30 °C under vacuum.

(3) **Direct Compression:** This is a simple and the most economical method. In this method, the drug and other components are compressed without any preliminary treatment. The concentration of the disintegrant has a great impact and is inversely proportional to the disintegration time. This method can be useful for a limited number of drugs.

(4) **Sublimation:** The principle involved in the formulation of MDTs by sublimation is the addition of a volatile salt to the tableting components. This results in a homogeneous mixture; removal of volatile salts creates pores in the tablet. This helps in rapid disintegration in the mouth. The drugs that can be formulated by using this method are camphor, Naphthalene, etc.

Patented technologies for mouth-dissolving tablets:

(1) **ZyduS Technologies:** This Technology was discovered by R P Scherer, a subsidiary of Cardinal Health. In this method, the drug is lyophilized and freeze-dried in water water-

soluble matrix material like gelatin. It is a self-preserving formulation as the water concentration in the freeze-dried product is very less. This prevents microbial contamination.

(2) **Orasolv technologies:** This was prepared by CIMA labs. Orasolv is a slightly effervescent tablet, as it can rapidly dissolve in the mouth. the active ingredients are dispersed in saliva due to the action of the effervescent agent, resulting in taste masking. The major disadvantage of this method is low mechanical strength. the formulated tablets need to be packed in a specially designed pack because they are very soft and fragile in nature.

(3) **Durasolv technologies:** These are second-generation mouth dissolving tablets by CIMA Labs. It is similar to Orasolv technology but has a much higher mechanical strength. The product formulated using this technology is fast and cost-effective. One of the major disadvantages of this technology is compatibility problems with large doses of active ingredients. this technology is currently available in two products, namely Nulev and Zorlip.

(4) **Wowtab technologies:** This technology was discovered by Yamanouchi. Wow means “Without water”. Wowtab technology is an intrabuccal soluble. This compressed tablet consists of granules made with saccharides of low and high mouldability. Mouldability

PATENTS ON MOUTH-DISSOLVING TABLETS¹⁰:

There is an account of some recent patents in the field of mouth-dissolving tablets, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Patents on mouth-dissolving tablets

Patented Technology	Process Involved	Patent Owner	Patent Number	Drugs (Brand Names)	Drug Release	Advantages	Disadvantages
Zydis	Lyophilization	R.P. Scherer Inc.	U.S. Pat. Nos. 4,305,502, 4,371,516, 4,642,903 and 5,738,875	Loratidine (Claritin Reditab and Dimetapp Quick Dissolve)	Dissolves in 2- 10 sec	Quick dissolution, Self-preserving, and increased bioavailability	Expensive process, poor stability at higher temperatures and humidity
Orasolv	Compressed Tablets	Cima Labs Inc.	U.S. Patent No. 5,178,878	Paracetamol (Tempra Quicklets), Zolmitriptan (Zolmig Repimelt)	Disintegrate in 5-45 sec	Taste-masking is twofold: quick dissolution	Low mechanical strength
Flashdose	Cotton-candy process	Fuisz Technology Ltd.	U.S. Pat. Nos. 5,587,172, 5,616,344, and 5,622,719	Tramadol HCl (Relivia Flash dose)	Dissolves within 1 min	High surface area for dissolution	High temperature required to melt the matrix can limit the use of heat-sensitive drugs, sensitive to moisture and humidity.
Wowtab	Compressed Moulded Tablets	Yamanouchi Pharma Technologies, Inc.	US Patent 5,466,464 and US Patent 5,576,014	Famotidine (Gaster D)	Disintegrate in 5-45 sec	Adequate dissolution rate and hardness	No significant change in bioavailability
Advatab	Microcaps and diffuscap CR Technology	Eurand International	U.S. Pat. No. 6,139,865	AdvaTab cetirizine, AdvaTab Paracetamol	Disintegrates in less than 30 seconds	Rapid Disintegration Without Water and Taste Masking Capability	Limited API Compatibility, Moisture Sensitivity
Durasolv	Molding	Cima Labs Inc.	US 6,024,981	Hyoscyamine Sulphate (NuLev)	Disintegrate in 5-45 sec	Higher mechanical strength than Orasolv, Good rigidity	Inappropriate with a larger dose
Ziplets	Molding	Eurand	WO 99/44580	Ibuprofen (Cibalgina Due Fast)	Disintegrate in 20 seconds in the mouth	Good mechanical strength, satisfactory properties can be obtained at high dose (450 mg) and high weight (850 mg)	As the soluble component dissolves, the rate of water diffusion into tablet is decreased because of the formation of a viscous concentrated solution
Lyoc	Multiparticulate Compressed Tablets	Farmlyoc	US 4,616,047 and US 5,843,347	Phloroglucinol Hydrate (Spasfon Lyoc)	Disintegrates in less than 10 seconds	Fast disintegration, patient compliance	Low drug load, expensive manufacturing

MARKETED PRODUCTS OF MOUTH DISSOLVING TABLETS

Some of the marketed products of mouth dissolving tablets are illustrated in Table 6.

Table 6: Marketed products of mouth-dissolving tablets

Drugs	Product	Super-disintegrants	Manufactured By	Uses	Images
Olanzapine	Zyprexa Zydis	Crosspovidone	Eli Lilly and Company	<i>It is an atypical antipsychotic primarily used to treat schizophrenia and bipolar disorder.</i>	
Ondansetron	Zofran ODT	Crosscarmellose	Glaxo Smith Kilne (GSK)	It is used to prevent nausea and vomiting caused by cancer medicines(chemotherapy) or radiation therapy.	
Alprazolam	Niravam	Crospovidone	Schwarz Pharma	It is used as a CNS Depressant and is used to treat anxiety and panic disorders	
Donepezil	Aricept ODT	Crosspovidone	Eisai Inc.	It is used to treat dementia and Alzheimer's disease.	
Rizatriptan benzoate	Maxalt MLT	Crospovidone, Carboxymethylcellulose calcium,	Merck and Co.	It is used in the acute treatment of migraine with or without aura.	
Aripiprazole	Abilify Discmelt	Croscarmellose sodium, Crospovidone	Otsuka America/ Bristol-Myers Squibb	It is used to treat schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, depression, and Tourette's disorder.	

Lansoprazole	Prevacid SoluTab	Crospovidone, Microcrystalline cellulose, Hydroxypropyl cellulose	Takeda Pharmaceuticals	It is used to treat duodenal and gastric ulcers, erosive esophagitis, and gastroesophageal reflux disease	
Metoclopramide hydrochloride	Reglan ODT	Crospovidone, microcrystalline cellulose	Oaknet Healthcare Pvt Ltd	It is used to treat nausea, vomiting, indigestion, and heartburn.	
Carbidopa levodopa	Parcopa	Crospovidone, Microcrystalline cellulose	Schwarz Pharma	It is used to treat symptoms of Parkinson's disease.	
Risperidone	Risperdal M-Tab	Microcrystalline cellulose, Hypromellose,	Janssen	It is used to treat schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, and irritability.	

CONCLUSION^{11,12}:

The MDTs have potential advantages over conventional oral dosage forms as they have improved patient compliance, rapid onset of action, and bioavailability. Various drugs that have limited bioavailability, high permeability, or that degrade rapidly in the stomach can be successfully formulated in the form of MDTs, as these tablets are absorbed through the oral cavity. MDTs are developed for most of the drugs, like anti-coagulants, anti-gout, anti-thyroid, anti-neoplastic agents, etc. Various manufacturing and evaluation techniques for MDTs are available due to advancements in technology. The research process is still going on for some categories of drugs that are not available in such dosage forms, i.e., MDTs.

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